

Free-space reconstruction of the electrical properties of carbon nanotube based composites in the Q-band range

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Abstract — A free-space transmission-reflection measurement method for the non-destructive electrical characterization of carbon nanotube based composites was developed. Specifically, this versatile method measures the dielectric properties of the sample in the Q-band, corresponding to a frequency range of 30 GHz to 50 GHz, and can be used with specimens that are either thinner or thicker than the radiation penetration depth. This method also involves an error correction model in order to accurately reconstruct the constitutive dielectric properties of the composites from the measured scattering parameters. In order to perform the error-correction only two reference scattering parameters measurements are required: one from a metal plate of known reflection coefficient and the other from air with no specimen. The simplicity of our error-correction model makes the method attractive for research, development, and for quality control in the manufacturing environment.

Index Terms — Free space measurement; microwave error-correction model; nanocarbon composites; non-destructive testing

I. INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) composites have been incorporated in a wide range of applications, especially in the aerospace and automotive industries [1-3]. The mechanical, thermal, and electrical properties of these composites are predominantly determined by the properties of the CNTs and their dispersion in the embedding polymer matrix [2-3]. A technique to evaluate the properties of these composites is based on quantifying the free-space microwave scattering parameters.

However, free-space microwave characterization is plagued by the mismatch between the two antennas and free space, the multiple reflections between the antennas and the material under test (MUT), and the diffraction of the waves in free space. Therefore, free space systems require elaborate procedures to extract the electrical properties of the MUT. These procedures can involve the movement of the antennas,

the movement of the MUT, and the measurement of the scattering parameters from multiple references [4-5].

One of the standard calibration techniques is the Thru-Reflect-Line (TRL) calibration technique [4-5]. However, the main challenge in this calibration is the need to move the antennas disturbing the alignment/coupling between them. The Line-Network-Network (LNN) procedure is another calibration technique that does not require a reflect standard [5]. Instead, this methodology corrects the measurement using four measurements: one thru and three MUT locations separated by an equal distance Δx [5]. However, it is difficult to implement the multiple shifting of the MUT in the quality control of high-thru-put unrolling thin film materials in a manufacturing line.

In this paper, we present a free-space Q-band experimental system for non-destructive non-contact characterization of CNT composites. For this system, we have devised a simple and accurate error correction model that mitigates the limitations of the previous calibration techniques. Only two reference scattering parameters measurements are required: one from a metal plate of known reflection coefficient and the other from air with no specimen. The use of microwaves in the Q-band, defined to be between 30 GHz and 50 GHz, is a broadband technique that is capable of providing both the real and imaginary parts of the complex dielectric permittivity constant, which can be related to the dispersion of the CNTs in the polymer matrix. The technique is relatively simple and, therefore, attractive for non-destructive quality control in the manufacturing environment.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Our Q-band non-contact microwave measurement system utilizes two horn antennas connected to a vector network analyzer. The distance between the antennas was 225 mm and the beam radius at the MUT plane in the middle between the antennas was roughly 52.5 mm. A holder, with an aperture in its center larger than the beam width, was utilized and

attached to a motorized stage for precise positioning of the MUT between the antennas. All the MUTs considered in this work had lateral dimensions of 300 mm x 300 mm or larger minimizing surface wave propagation and parasitic edge effects.

III. ERROR CORRECTION MODEL

The scattering parameters of the MUT $\{T_{11}, T_{21}, T_{22}, T_{12}\}$ are measured by the system, which is initially calibrated at the coaxial ends connected to the antennas (see Fig. 1). Therefore, the measurements are affected by propagation through antennas A1 and A2, as well as propagation in free space between the antennas and interfaces 1 and 2. In order to account for these effects and move the reference planes of the measurements from the coaxial ends to the plane of the MUT, two additional measurements are performed using references with known propagation characteristics. Specifically, these references are (i) a *metal* plate, for which we denote the scattering parameters as $\{M_{11}, M_{21}, M_{22}, M_{12}\}$ and (ii) the scattering parameters from *air* or where no MUT is inserted between the two antennas, $\{L_{11}, L_{21}, L_{22}, L_{12}\}$. The corrected transmission, S_{21}^{MUT} , and the corrected reflection, S_{11}^{MUT} , from the MUT are:

$$S_{21}^{MUT} = \frac{G[T_{21}]}{G[L_{21}]} e^{-j\beta_0 d} \quad (1)$$

$$S_{11}^{MUT} = \frac{G[T_{11} - L_{11}]}{G[M_{11} - L_{11}]} (-1), \quad (2)$$

where G refers to time gating, d is the MUT thickness, $j^2 = -1$ is the imaginary unit and $\beta_0 = \omega/c_0$ is the calculated plane wave propagation factor in air. The time gating correction is performed by transforming the scattering parameters measurements from frequency domain to the time domain using the Inverse Fast Fourier Transform (IFFT). The first reflection/transmission is then isolated by multiplying the time domain measurement with a Gaussian window centered at the same time instant as the maximum of the first reflection/transmission. The width of the Gaussian window, typically in the range of about 15 ns, is selected to reject any additional spurious multiple reflections/transmissions.

In (1), the denominator $G[L_{21}]$ normalizes S_{21}^{MUT} and deconvolutes the antenna response, while $e^{-j\beta_0 d}$ adjusts the reference plane to interface 2 of the MUT. In (2), the subtraction of L_{11} removes any mismatch between the antenna and the connecting cable whereas the division with $G[M_{11} - L_{11}]$ normalizes the reflection from the MUT, S_{11}^{MUT} . The metal plate reference reflects all the incident waves and, therefore, it is assumed to have a reflection magnitude of unity. The multiplication by -1 in (2) is performed to account for the fact that the reflection from the metal plate is 180° out of phase from the incident wave. Following the correction of S_{21}^{MUT} and S_{11}^{MUT} using (1) and (2), the complex relative

Fig. 1. Sketch of the experimental setup with (a) the MUT and (b) the calibrating metal plate inserted between the two antennas.

dielectric permittivity $\epsilon_r = \epsilon_r' + j\epsilon_r''$ can be extracted through a root searching algorithm [5-6].

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In order to validate our error correction model, which is summarized in (1) and (2), we used a poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) MUT with known complex relative dielectric permittivity $\epsilon_r \approx 2.5$ [7]. The PMMA MUT had a thickness $d = 1.95$ mm. The measured transmission and reflection from the MUT were corrected using (1) and (2) and the corresponding ϵ_r are plotted in Fig. 2. For comparison, the LNN procedure reported in [5] was used to correct the measured scattering parameters and the corresponding value of ϵ_r is also plotted in Fig. 2. The LNN error-correction model does not involve a *metal* plate standard and, therefore, is completely independent from our error-correction model developed in (1) and (2). The close agreement between both values of the complex relative dielectric permittivity ϵ_r in Fig. 2 validates our error-correction model. Furthermore, the reconstructed permittivity values are in good agreement with those reported for Plexiglas in [7].

In Fig. 3 we present the complex permittivity of a lossy CNT composite having thickness $d = 1.95$ mm. Fig. 3 shows that the CNT composite has a significant imaginary part in the relative permittivity indicating considerable losses. Again, good agreement is achieved between the simple calibration developed herein and the LNN calibration. Even though the MUT in Fig. 3 was lossy, the skin depth of the CNT composite is larger than the MUT thickness and, therefore,

significant S_{21}^{MUT} was measured. These MUTs are labelled as microwave transparent in comparison to microwave nontransparent MUTs with negligible S_{21}^{MUT} . We also measured other CNT composites with skin depth comparable to or less than the MUT thickness from which S_{21}^{MUT} is negligible. These results will also be presented.

V. UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS

Several uncertainty factors such as instrumentation, dimensional uncertainty of the MUT geometry, and roughness of the MUT surfaces contribute to the combined uncertainty of the measurements. Typically, the standard uncertainty in the measured scattering parameters can be assumed to be within the manufacturer's specification for the network analyzer, about ± 0.05 dB for the magnitude and $\pm 0.5^\circ$ for the phase. The largest contributing factor to the combined uncertainty is the uncertainty in the distribution of the film thickness and/or sagging of the thin film MUT, which is depicted by the bending in the interfaces of the MUT in the sketch shown in Fig. 1. The error-correction model assumes that the interfaces of the MUT and the metal plate are placed at precisely the same location. However, any thickness inhomogeneity or sagging in the thin film MUT can lead to a shift between the locations of the interfaces of the MUT and the interfaces of the metal plate. This shift is shown as Δ_s in Fig. 1 and can distort the error correction model. However, this shift is on the order of $\Delta_s < 100 \mu\text{m}$, which can be estimated to cause a maximum uncertainty of 5% in ϵ_r .

VI. MODELING OF THE ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON NANOTUBE COMPOSITES

To help understand the experimental microwave measurements from CNT composites detailed in the previous sections, composite 2D models of CNTs embedded in a dielectric slab are developed similar to those reported in [8]. The basis of the model was to implement the CNT composite as multiple random arrays of infinitesimally thin wire antennas with the equivalent impedance of CNT. These random wire arrays were then embedded in a dielectric slab to account for the effect of the matrix of the composite on the electromagnetic signature of the CNTs. The model showed that the reflected power from the composite was sensitive to the exact locations of the CNTs and to their locations with respect to the interfaces of the dielectric slab [8]. This sensitivity to the location is one of the possible explanations for the variability in the measurements from different CNT composites exhibited in this work.

VII. CONCLUSION

A Simple free-space calibration technique for the reconstruction of the relative dielectric properties of carbon nanotube based composites is developed and verified in the Q-

Fig. 2: Complex relative dielectric permittivity of a PMMA specimen obtained using the correction model in (1) and (2) (real ϵ_r' shown as Δ and imaginary ϵ_r'' shown as \times) versus the LNN calibration (real ϵ_r' shown as \circ and imaginary ϵ_r'' shown as \square).

Fig. 3: Complex relative dielectric permittivity of a microwave transparent CNT composite obtained using the correction model in (1) and (2) (real ϵ_r' shown as Δ and imaginary ϵ_r'' shown as \times) versus the LNN calibration (real ϵ_r' shown as \circ and imaginary ϵ_r'' shown as \square).

band. The presented error correction procedure involves only two reference measurements: a *metal* plate and *air* with no MUT present. The reconstructed relative dielectric properties agree favorably with the values achieved using the previously reported LNN calibration technique, which requires four measurements, three MUT locations and an air measurement with no MUT present. In the future, we will develop electromagnetic models to correlate the measured dielectric properties with the constituents and internal structure of the CNT composites.

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